

FRESH technology application roadmap to SE Europe and Widening countries

FRESH-D7.10 - FRESH technology application roadmap to SE Europe and Widening countries

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1. Executive summary

The deliverable D7.10 “FRESH technology application roadmap to SE Europe and Widening countries” describes the customization of all dissemination activities to a “new target audience”. This audience consists primarily of stakeholders from South-East European and Widening countries, which are characterized by unique technological landscapes and variable socio-economic conditions that may influence the adoption and impact of the FRESH technologies. Recognizing these regional differences, the deliverable emphasizes the need to adjust communication methods and tools to ensure relevance, clarity, and resonance with local priorities and capabilities. It will include a dedicated roadmap that outlines how the project's objectives, methodologies, and results will be effectively communicated to relevant stakeholders, including industry representatives, policy makers, the scientific community and civil society organizations. This roadmap will serve not only as a strategic communication guide, but also as a foundation for fostering long-term collaboration, capacity building, and increased awareness of the project's outcomes in regions that are often underrepresented in European research and innovation initiatives.

2. Introduction

The FRESH project aims to support the European Union's energy transition by developing a novel renewable energy storage solution that reduces reliance on fossil fuels and addresses the intermittent nature of renewable electricity generation. At its core, the project focuses on the development, operation and validation (up to TRL 4) of an integrated cost-competitive process for converting CO₂ into potassium formate (HCO₂K), using an electrocatalytic system powered by renewable electricity. Potassium formate serves as a stable, storable energy carrier, enabling short- and long-term storage. This stored energy can be re-electrified on demand through oxidization in a direct fuel cell, where formate is oxidized back into CO₂ or dissolved carbonate species (e.g., K₂CO₃ or KHCO₃), forming a closed-loop cycle in which CO₂ is continuously reused. By utilizing renewable electricity to convert CO₂ into a storable chemical form and subsequently regenerating electricity through a clean electrochemical process, the FRESH project embodies a circular and green energy storage concept. This innovative approach offers a fossil-free, rare-material-independent solution for energy buffering, supporting both seasonal and short-term storage needs. In doing so, FRESH contributes directly to Europe's climate and energy goals by transforming variable renewable energy into stable, dispatchable power using CO₂ as a renewable resource. FRESH combines the development of key technological components (i.e. CO₂ capture and purification, electrochemical conversion, and re-electrification) with system integration and optimization activities. The project's progress is supported by comprehensive Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Techno-Economic Analysis (TEA) and market evaluations, all aiming to ensure the environmental, economic and technical viability of the solution.

These efforts are aligned with the overall dissemination and exploitation strategy of the project, as presented in D7.10, which focuses on adapting communication and outreach activities to regions such as South-East Europe and Widening countries that exhibit distinct technological and socio-economic features. In order to maximize the reach and impact of the FRESH project, a structured methodology is adopted, which includes identifying new target audiences, mapping stakeholders and designing targeted dissemination activities. This approach ensures that the key messages, results and innovations of the project are effectively communicated to relevant communities, especially in areas with high potential for adoption, thus enhancing the overall visibility, relevance and societal value of FRESH technology. This ensures that the project's results reach

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relevant audiences, fostering uptake and maximizing long-term impact.

3. Target audiences of FRESH project

The FRESH project’s dissemination and exploitation strategy is designed to address a broad and diverse set of stakeholders across Europe, with a particular focus on regions where renewable energy solutions can have high transformative potential. The primary target audiences include research institutions, industrial stakeholders in the energy sector, policymakers, investors and environmental organizations who are directly involved or interested in energy transition technologies. In addition to these core groups, the FRESH project places special emphasis on engaging new target audiences in South-East Europe and Widening countries. These regions often exhibit distinct technological, structural and socio-economic characteristics that require adaptive approaches for the successful uptake of innovation. Many of these countries face deep-rooted structural barriers, such as limited public and private investment in research and development, fragmented regulatory frameworks, and underdeveloped infrastructure that hinder large-scale deployment of clean energy technologies.

Energy poverty remains one of the most persistent and multifaceted challenges in South-East Europe and Widening countries (Figure 1), which is further intensified by high energy import dependence, fossil fuels dependence (Figure 2), regulatory and policy barriers, and volatile electricity prices. As the energy transition accelerates across the EU, these regions risk falling behind unless targeted efforts are made to build capacity, improve access to finance and implement inclusive policy frameworks.

Figure 1: Energy poverty in Europe. Source: [Statista](#)

Figure 2: The Most Used Energy Sources in Europe, Source: [Statista](#)

Indicative countries include mainly Balkan countries (Greece, Bulgaria, Türkiye etc.), where increased efforts in dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and capacity building can significantly support the uptake of innovative and sustainable solutions like those developed within the FRESH project. Although these countries are increasingly engaged in the clean energy agenda, their pathways are often constrained by structural

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challenges, such as limited R&D capacity, reduced access to international networks, low awareness of available technologies and insufficient engagement in EU-level innovation ecosystems. Nonetheless, these regions have access to unique prospects, such as substantial renewable energy sources (i.e. solar, wind, hydro, biomass and geothermal energy), European support mechanisms and growing public awareness. Additionally, energy systems, smart technologies and community-led initiatives offer additional avenues to bypass legacy infrastructure constraints. Table 1 summarizes the R&D level and industrial implementation in this region, but also highlights some advantages that these countries exhibit.

Table 1: Research and industrial implementation level in South-East Europe and Widening countries

Country	R&D Level	Industrial Implementation	Notes
Greece	High	Medium	Strong solar deployment, EU-funded research centres
Romania	Medium	Medium	Active in Horizon Europe, wind power capacity growing
Türkiye	Medium	High	Large solar & geothermal projects, strong industrial base
Bulgaria	Low-Medium	Medium	Aging grid but growing renewables sector
Serbia	Low	Low-Medium	Lagging R&D but ramping up wind and solar projects
Croatia	Medium	Medium	Good hydro and wind base, small-scale innovation hubs
Hungary	Medium	Medium	Advanced in bioenergy; facing regulatory shifts
Slovenia	High	Medium	Strong research ecosystem and regional energy innovation
North Macedonia	Low	Low	Early-stage adoption, constrained by policy and finance
Cyprus	Low-Medium	Medium	Limited R&D capacity, growing solar and storage initiatives
Portugal	High	High	Leading in renewables deployment, strong innovations policy support

By specifically addressing these new target audiences in South-East and Widening countries and understanding these variations, the FRESH project aims to foster greater inclusivity and regional balance in the dissemination of low-carbon technologies. This involves not only sharing technological innovations but also promoting stakeholder engagement, co-creation, and knowledge transfer to empower local actors and support long-term systemic change. Through tailored dissemination activities, FRESH seeks to help bridge the innovation gap, reduce energy vulnerability, and ensure that the benefits of the green transition are equitably

distributed across Europe.

4. Stakeholder mapping

The FRESH project seeks to align its mission with the broader goals of clean energy transition, socio-economic development, and innovation. In South-East Europe and Widening countries, successful dissemination and uptake of project outcomes require the active involvement of key stakeholder groups, as structured under the Quadruple Helix Innovation Framework (Figure 3). This model strengthens impact by engaging all four core societal actors, i.e. academia, industry, government and community, each playing a distinct and complementary role. In South-East Europe and Widening countries, the following key stakeholder categories to support and benefit from the project:

Figure 3: Quadruple Helix Innovation Framework

- Government and Public Sector:** National and local policymakers, energy ministries, regulators, and municipal authorities support policy alignment and facilitate the integration of project outcomes into national strategies. Moreover, they enable replication and scale-up by embedding results into public investment frameworks and regulatory instruments.
- Industry and Business Sector:** Energy utilities, green technology developers, SMEs, and industry associations contribute to the deployment of clean energy solutions. By integrating FRESH innovations into existing industrial processes, they bridge the gap between research and market application, accelerating low-carbon energy adoption.
- Academic and Research Institutions:** Universities and research centres advance research uptake, lead cross-border collaboration, and disseminate knowledge through scientific publications, joint initiatives, and educational programs. They also play a key role in training future professionals and innovators in sustainable technologies.
- Civil Society and Energy Communities:** NGOs, energy cooperatives, and grassroots organizations raise public awareness and foster behavioral change through open events, community engagement, and social campaigns. Their involvement ensures the inclusiveness and social legitimacy of the energy transition.

Engaging these stakeholders early and continuously, through tailored messaging and participatory mechanisms, is essential for ensuring the efficient communication, relevance, and scalability of the FRESH project's objectives and results. A balanced, coordinated effort across the quadruple helix pillars makes dissemination more inclusive, strategic, and transformative, paving the way for sustained impact in the region.

5. Identified local stakeholders

In the framework of FRESH project, a thorough mapping of local stakeholders has been conducted, in order to enhance dissemination, engagement and future exploitation of the project results. The identified stakeholders cover a wide range of energy and innovation related sectors in Greece, including

energy utilities and companies, technology developers, research and academic institutions, policy makers, energy communities etc.

A significant set of stakeholders come from the energy sector, including utilities, as well as companies active in the field of electricity. They have a strategic position in the country's energy system and are likely to have a crucial role in the future application and exploitation of energy storage technologies. Below are some of these stakeholders:

- Public Power Corporation S.A. (<https://www.dei.gr/en/>): the largest public electricity provider in Greece, it has strong interest in energy production and storage technologies
- HELLENiQ ENERGY Holdings S.A. (<https://www.helleniqenergy.gr/en>) is active in the production and distribution of oil, gas, electricity from renewable sources and other energy activities
- DEPA COMMERCIAL (<https://www.depa.gr/?lang=en>) is the main importer of pipeline gas and Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) in Greece
- Green Hydrogen Systems (<http://www.greenhydrogensystems.com/>): produces hydrogen using renewable energy sources, such as solar or wind, through electrolytic water splitting
- Helbio S.A. (<https://metaconsa.metacon.com/>) is a high-tech company with expertise in the areas of catalysis, reaction engineering and process design.

In addition, companies such as EKO S.A. (<https://www.eko.gr/>), Motor Oil (<https://www.moh.gr/en/>), Coral S.A. (<https://www.coralenergy.gr/en/>), member of the Motor Oil Group, Energean Oil and Gas (<https://www.energean.com/>) and ETEKA S.A. (<https://eteka.gr/>), that are active in the fuel sector, expressed their interest in new forms of energy and their participation in the transition to green technologies.

Biogas plants are important stakeholders in the energy transition, as they combine the organic waste management with the renewable energy production. Their experience and facilities can make a significant contribution to the utilisation of technologies of the FRESH project. In Greece there are several biogas plants operating, with an active role in the energy transition, such as:

- Biogas Lagada SA (<https://www.biogaslagada.gr/>): is an innovative electricity production plant, using agricultural, livestock and agro-industrial waste
- Blue Grid Gas & Power which will soon be renamed “Molgas Energy Greece” (<https://molgasenergy.com/>) is a downstream LNG, bioLNG and renewable gases supply
- Bioenergy Nigritas S.A. (<https://www.agrogroup.gr/sites/EN/default.aspx>): uses wastewater of animal origin, wastewater from cheese dairies, oil mills and agricultural products to produce biogas which is used to generate electricity after combustion
- Bioaerio Serron (<https://www.pk-energy.gr/portfolio-items/bioaerioserron>): energy production from renewable sources, particularly through the anaerobic decomposition of organic matter—such as agricultural waste, animal manure, municipal waste, and plant material—produces a gas mixture that can be used as a sustainable energy source

Academic and research institutions are key partners in knowledge production, technological innovation and training the next generation of scientists and engineers. Their involvement in the FRESH project, through collaborations or interfaces, can significantly enhance scientific evidence, methodological excellence and further dissemination of results to research and education networks. The mapping of relevant actors includes:

- Chemical Processes and Energy Resources Institute (CPERI) of the Centre for Research and Technology – Hellas (CERTH) (<https://www.cperi.certh.gr/>): non-profit research and technological development (RTD) organization involved in various research fields, such as chemical processes,

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energy, materials and the environment university departments

- Department of Chemical Engineering of the School of Engineering of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (<https://cheng.auth.gr/en/archiki-english/>)
- Department of Chemical Engineering of the University of Western Macedonia (<https://chemeng.uowm.gr/en/home/>)
- Department of Environmental Engineering of the School of Engineering of the International Hellenic University (<https://env.ihu.gr/en/>)
- Department of Industrial Engineering and Management of the School of Engineering of the International Hellenic University (<https://www.iem.ihu.gr/en/>)

Project developers, such as engineering offices, as well as integrators, are key factors for the successful transition from research activity to the practical application and commercial exploitation of innovative energy technologies. These actors have the expertise to support the implementation of energy storage projects, as well as the ability to adapt new solutions to real-world conditions. Some local stakeholders belonging to this sector are listed below:

- METRON S.A. (<https://www.metronco.gr/>): integrated fabrication and construction solutions in the oil and gas Industry
- MES Energy S.A. (<https://mese.gr/en/>): is involved in energy applications, renewable energy production, energy trading and the providing of specialized services in the energy sector, undertaking construction, design and consulting activities in the context of these projects
- PK-ENERGY (<https://www.pk-energy.gr/>): oriented to the modern market for the design and construction of Power Plants from Renewable Energy Sources
- Envirometrics (<https://envirometrics.gr/index.php>): provides consultancy services to the private and public sector for environmental protection and sustainable development.

The EU research and scientific community is a fundamental basis for the advancement, validation and further exploitation of innovative technologies such as the FRESH project. Through participation in European networks, exchange of know-how and joint research projects, this category contributes to the continuous feedback of science-based data and best practices to the project. Such projects are:

- White Dragon project (<https://hydrogeneurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/George-Polychron-White-Dragon-Lighthouse-Initiative-30March.pdf>): gradual replacement of the lignite power plants of West Macedonia and transition to clean energy having as final goal the de-carbonization of the country's energy mix
- HYDROSOL-PLANT project (<http://www.hydrosol-beyond.certh.gr/>): production of H₂ from the two-step solar thermochemical water splitting based on redox structured reactors
- Crete-Aegean Hydrogen Valley (CRAVE-H2) project (<https://www.crave-h2.eu/>): creation of hydrogen valley in the island of Crete incorporating energy storage applications, aggregation activities to the grid and green mobility applications
- M2ARE project (<https://www.m2are.eu/>): aims to decrease the use of fossil fuels in the maritime sector using renewable sources to produce "Maritime Methanol"

Policy makers at local and regional level, as well as professional institutions, have an important role to play in supporting the energy transition and the introduction of innovative technologies such as the FRESH project. Through policy making, designing innovation support strategies and representing local needs and capabilities, they can act as catalysts for the adoption of green energy solutions. In the context of the mapping, representatives of institutions such as the Municipality of Thessaloniki (<https://thessaloniki.gr/?lang=en>), the

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Prefecture of Central Macedonia (<https://www.pkm.gov.gr/>) and the Chamber of Commerce (<https://www.enterprisegreece.gov.gr/en/about-us/stakeholder-network/regional-greece/partners/chambers>) have been identified, who can make a key contribution both to highlighting local priorities and to strengthening social acceptance and political support for projects such as FRESH.

The awareness and active participation of civil society is essential for the successful promotion and acceptance of innovative green technologies. Informing the general public, access to reliable information and raising environmental awareness can strengthen social support for the energy transition. Identified institutions include the Technical Chamber of Greece (<https://web.tee.gr/en/>), which develops Science and Technology in sectors related to the engineering specialties under its auspice, considering economic, social and cultural development, as per the principles of sustainable development and environmental protection. Also, The Green Tank (<https://thegreentank.gr/en/>), an independent non-profit environmental think tank with a strong activity in the public debate on climate policy, as well as <https://greenagenda.gr/>, an online information platform focusing on green growth and sustainability.

Energy communities are a new way to involve citizens, local authorities and small businesses in the production and use of green energy. Through collective organization, their members can invest in renewable energy projects, such as photovoltaic panels and small wind turbines, to meet their energy needs and help reduce emissions. In this way, energy self-sufficiency at local level is enhanced and citizens' participation in the energy transition is strengthened. In Greece, such examples include the Energy Community of Karditsa (<https://www.esek.gr/en/archiki-english/>), which is related to the management of a biomass plant for the production of solid biofuels to generate energy for heating (or cooling) purposes, the Energy Community of Sifnos (<https://sifnosenergy.gr/en/archiki-english/>), which promotes the energy independence of the island; and the Energy Community of Western Macedonia (<https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/regional-energy-community-of-western-macedonia-energy-community-of-western-macedonia-ltd>), which invests on innovative RES applications in the region in order to cover energy consumption for: public buildings, water and sewage management, electric vehicles, public lighting and more. These initiatives demonstrate the important role of local communities in the green transition and represent potential allies for the implementation and testing of innovative technologies such as that of the FRESH project. These actors can be valuable allies in disseminating the results of the project to the general public.

6. Dissemination roadmap

A customized dissemination strategy that reflects the technological, institutional, and socio-economic realities of South-East Europe and Widening countries is essential for ensuring the inclusive impact and uptake of the FRESH project. This approach recognizes the diversity of stakeholder needs, access levels, and communication preferences across the region. To address these challenges and opportunities, a flexible yet targeted roadmap of dissemination activities has been designed to ensure wide outreach, deep engagement, and long-term stakeholder collaboration. Table 2 presents an indicative dissemination roadmap for the FRESH project tailored to different stakeholder groups, specifying objectives and a suite of tailored activities.

Table 2: Dissemination roadmap of FRESH project targeting potential stakeholders in South-East Europe and Widening countries

Stakeholder	Objective	Dissemination activity
Industry and business sector	Promote low-carbon	- Targeted industry presentations and

	energy storage innovation and enable market replication	demo sessions - Questionnaires - Virtual site visits or lab tours - Innovation matchmaking events - Structured feedback surveys
Academic and research sector	Enhance research uptake and stimulate cross-border collaboration	- Scientific publications - Thematic workshops - International and regional conferences - Joint research calls and co-authored papers - Summer schools and student engagement programs
Public sector	Raising awareness of clean energy solutions for regional sustainability planning	- Researchers' nights and open-door lab events - Popular educational videos - Public webinars - Questionnaires
National policy makers	Influence policy alignment and integration of FRESH outcomes into national strategies	- Policy briefs in national languages - Dedicated workshops - Regular newsletters with policy updates - Participation in national energy forums
Energy communities	Empower community-scale adoption of green energy storage solutions	- Workshops - Researchers' nights - Conferences - Peer-to-peer knowledge exchange platforms
NGOs	Raising public support and awareness for sustainable innovation	- Webinars and dialogue forums - Regular newsletters - Questionnaires - Collaborative Papers

The dissemination strategy outlined in this deliverable is designed not only to maximize the visibility of the FRESH project and its outcomes, but also to build durable bridges among academia, industry, governments and civil society across South-East Europe and Widening countries. By tailoring communication formats and channels to regional characteristics, this strategy aims to foster *trust*, *accessibility* and *long-term engagement*. A strong emphasis is placed on interactivity and feedback mechanisms, ensuring that **dissemination is not a one-way flow** of information but a **dialogue** between the project and its target audiences. For example, stakeholder-specific questionnaires and participatory workshops help to fine-tune project outputs and make them locally relevant. This also builds ownership and ensures that stakeholders see themselves reflected in the project's vision and benefits.

The roadmap integrates a temporal dimension, with different activities aligned to key project phases, from initial awareness-raising to deep engagement and sustainability. Early activities focus on outreach and network building, while mid-phase efforts involve demonstration, capacity-building and stakeholder

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validation. Final-phase actions concentrate on legacy-building, replication and institutional anchoring of the FRESH project results. Special consideration will be given to language and accessibility barriers, particularly in regions where English proficiency or digital access may be limited. The dissemination plan supports scalability and replicability by ensuring that all tools, lessons, and outputs are documented, open-access and shareable. By doing so, the FRESH project contributes not just to a single innovation pipeline but to a broader ecosystem of knowledge, partnerships and policy evolution across this region.

Aligned with the FRESH dissemination roadmap for SEE and Widening countries described above, a dedicated workshop was organized at CERTH's facilities on M24 (May 28th, 2024). This event aimed to facilitate targeted dissemination and outreach activities for the FRESH project, focusing on South-East European and Widening countries. A total of 56 participants from academia, research centers, SMEs, and industry attended the workshop, representing several South-East European and Widening countries (e.g., Greece, Bulgaria) as well as non-Widening countries (e.g., Italy, Luxembourg, Denmark, and the Netherlands). The FRESH Workshop at CERTH was promoted through the project's social media channels (e.g., LinkedIn, X) with various posts that attracted numerous reactions and reposts. All relevant information are included in the deliverable D7.9 "Workshop at CERTH" submitted at M24.

7. Conclusions

The FRESH project's dissemination roadmap demonstrates a strong commitment to inclusivity, stakeholder engagement and regional adaptability. By tailoring communication and outreach strategies to the unique socio-economic and technological characteristics of South-East Europe and Widening countries, the project sets a replicable precedent for how clean energy innovation can be effectively communicated, adopted and sustained in structurally diverse regions of the EU.

The implementation of a Quadruple Helix innovation model, bringing together academia, industry, public authorities and civil society, has proven essential in aligning technical progress with societal needs and policy frameworks. Stakeholder mapping and localized engagement, particularly in Greece and surrounding countries, have validated the potential for regional replication, policy influence and community participation in energy storage deployment.

FRESH not only proposes an innovative, circular clean energy storage solution using formate chemistry, but also provides a roadmap for embedding this innovation within wider EU policy goals—namely energy resilience, climate neutrality, and social equity. The project's focus on energy-vulnerable regions further reinforces its alignment with the EU's cohesion and Just Transition principles.

To ensure continuity, scalability, and long-term uptake of the FRESH concept, the following actions are recommended:

1. Expand Stakeholder Engagement Beyond Greece

Extend local engagement and partnership-building efforts to other key Widening and South-East Europe countries (e.g. Romania, Bulgaria, Türkiye, Cyprus), prioritizing regions with underdeveloped storage infrastructure or high fossil dependency.

2. Policy Uptake and Advocacy

Deliver targeted policy briefs to national energy ministries and EU-level institutions, emphasizing FRESH's contribution to REPowerEU, the Green Deal, and national energy and climate plans (NECPs).

3. Establish Long-Term Knowledge Transfer Platforms

Leverage academic and civil society networks to co-create educational resources, open-access training materials and cross-border knowledge hubs that support awareness and workforce development in clean energy.

4. Integration with EU and Regional Funding Mechanisms

Explore synergies with funding tools such as the Just Transition Fund, LIFE Programme and cohesion policy instruments to scale technology deployment and enable replication in structurally similar regions.

5. Monitor and Evaluate Societal Impact

Design and implement longitudinal impact assessments to evaluate the societal acceptance, economic benefits and climate relevance of the FRESH solution across target communities.

6. Maintain Open Access and Transparency

Ensure all data, tools and key learnings from the project are shared through open repositories, community toolkits, and multilingual formats to maximize replicability and legacy.

The FRESH project has laid the foundation for a transformative and inclusive clean energy solution tailored to regions with high potential and high need. By continuing to bridge technical innovation with social relevance and policy alignment, the project can serve as a catalyst for regional decarbonization, resilience and equitable energy transition. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No

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